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Demonstrating the use of advanced materials and rethinking the innovation process in shipbuilding – Results of the RAMSSES project

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Abstract

Complicated and expensive approval processes as well as the challenge to efficiently combine new materials and processes with conventional ones are among the main reasons why the benefits of advanced (e.g. lightweight) materials have been exploited to a limited extent till now. The RAMSSES project aims to help overcoming existing barriers. Thirteen demonstrators, driven by industry, are developed, following today's approval methods, and built, aiming towards successful market entry. Various materials, ship types, application areas, and deployment strategies are covered. The demonstration includes the manufacturing of physical structures as well as the development of efficient approval processes which are required during production and other phases of products' lives. Assessment is done to show that regulatory and customer requirements are met.

Next to intermediate results from several demonstrators, the paper at hand discusses a set of measures to enhance material innovation in the maritime industry, including a 'smart track to approval'.

Keywords: Material innovation; Shipbuilding; Rules and regulations; Life Cycle Performance Assessment; Composite materials; Ship equipment

Nomenclature

AEL	Aviation Enterprises
AIP	Approval in Principle
AL	Assessment Layer
AM	Additive Manufacturing
DDL	Development and Demonstration Layer
DSNS	Damen Schelde Naval Shipyard
ECN	Ecole Centrale de Nantes
E-LASS	European network for lightweight applications at sea
FRP	Fibre reinforced plastics
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GFRP	Glass fibre reinforced plastics
HTS	High tensile steel
ICC	InfraCore Company
ICL	Information and Communication Layer
ISSC	International Ship and Offshore Structures Congress
LCPA	Life Cycle Performance Assessment
MIG-MAG	metal inert gas (MIG) / metal active gas (MAG) welding
NG	Naval Group
PAX	Passenger(s)
RAMSSES	Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable & Efficient Ships
RoRo	Roll on Roll off
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
STA	Smart track to approval
VARTM	Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding
WAAM	Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing

1. Introduction – Scope and objectives of the RAMSSES project

1.1. Background and motivation

It is widely accepted that the use of innovative materials in European built ships can provide a significant contribution to the reduction of GHG emissions in the transport chain and to improve ship performance, thereby maintaining the competitiveness of and employment in the European maritime industry. Despite significant progress and first successful commercial applications of lightweight structures, the market uptake of advanced materials is rather slow. With the ambition to overcome existing barriers, the European Innovation Action RAMSSES comprises both practical measures that are dedicated to improving, assessing and showing the readiness of certain technologies, and strategic actions that aim at enhancing the innovation capability of the European maritime industry on the long run and in a sustainable manner.

1.2. Challenges and objectives

Three specific project objectives have been defined to address the most relevant problems with respect to material innovation in the maritime industry as follow:

- Foster the use of new materials in real applications with high market potential.
- Prove full technical and economic feasibility of the solutions using best practice and consolidate knowledge.
- Support the maritime sector's innovation capabilities.

The first objective comes to answer the lack of confidence and awareness among ship operators, shipyards, and suppliers to uptake the potential innovative materials to bring benefits technically and economically. RAMSSES' answer was to initiate market driven demonstrators, which has led shipbuilders and sub-suppliers to construct thirteen demo cases covering the whole range from components, to integration of equipment, to repair processes. The demo cases are dedicated to showing the variety of innovative materials, their suitability for maritime applications and the related potential to optimize the entire process chain, to develop modular products, processes,

approval and application procedures, and to reduce cost while maintaining high flexibility. These effects will be validated by an accompanying economic and environmental performance assessment.

The second objective is to answer the lack of available information on the technical performance of innovative materials at lab scale and in realistic maritime environments. RAMSSES solution is to perform the technical assessment, including destructive testing and on-board measurements, and life cycle performance assessment (LCPA) in a harmonized way, using leading-edge expertise combined with tests where appropriate. Existing test results and experiences in maritime and other sectors are taken into account when documenting the results of approval tests in a common data repository for future use in similar cases.

The third objective is to support the innovation by providing a systematic knowledge and data repository, collecting project results and information from external sources. Furthermore, the collaboration with existing initiatives forms a Maritime Innovation Platform, which helps to spread excellence to a wider community. Experience in practical applications, test data, and efficient methodologies to prove equivalent safety for new materials will feed into the rulemaking process and improve the expertise of the sector. Each of the objectives corresponds with a set of activities which have been translated into layers of the ‘RAMSSES pyramid’, representing the project structure, Figure 1.

Figure 1 Layer structure within the RAMSSES project, and main objectives

1.3. Range of materials and applications

In RAMSSES, 13 different demonstrator cases (so-called demos) are being realised. As Table 1 shows, the demos cover a broad range of different materials (composites and metal), ship types (from small work or leisure boats to large cruise vessels) and application areas (components, equipment, complete hulls). The underlying business ideas range from standardisable parts which can be produced at high batches, to customised one-off solutions.

Table 1. Demonstrators in the RAMSSES project

Cluster title	Demonstrator title	Lead	Focus material	TRL target	Validation
Components & Equipment	Modular Light System for Less Critical Internal Walls and superstructure	BaltiCo	various	6-7	(pre)approval
	Lightweight Components for High Loads and Fire Class	PodComp	composite	6-7	(pre)approval
	Propeller blades by additive manufacturing	Naval Group	Metal	4-5	shore-based
	Lightweight Rudder Flap	Becker Marine Systems	composite	6-7	onboard
Ship integration: Composite	Integration of System for Internal Walls and Superstructure of Cruise Ships into shipyard processes	Meyer Werft	composite	7	onboard
	Modular Decks for RoRo vessels	Flow Ship Design	composite	7	onboard
	Lightweight aluminium and composite walls for Work Boats	MEC	various	6	onboard

	Composite superstructure module on steel deck for multi purpose vessels	Naval Group	composite	6	shore-based
	Multi-material lightweight cabin for passenger ships	Chantiers de l'Atlantique	various	6	shore-based
	Custom Made Hull for Offshore vessel	Damen Schelde Naval Shipyard	composite	6-7	shore-based
Ship integration: Steel & repair	Highly Loaded structural details from high tensile steel in passenger and research vessels	Fincantieri	Steel	6	shore-based
	Lightweight Decks using High Tensile Steel in cruise ships	Meyer Turku	Steel	7	onboard
	Composite Overlay to repair and improve metallic and non-metallic structures	Cardama	various	7	(pre)approval onboard

2. Progress of the demonstrators

Intermediate results from the demonstrators are presented in this section. The selected examples are covering both metallic materials and different kinds of composites. The application areas comprise ship equipment, standardizable components, and large customized structures, and the foreseen commercial applications are related to different ship types. Thus, the selection gives a good impression of the wide scope covered by the RAMSSES project.

2.1. Modular Lightweight system for less critical internal walls and superstructure

BaltiCo from Germany is coordinating this demonstrator. The objective is to create an ultra-low weight modular standard system consisting of panels, connecting elements and outfitting elements (e.g. doors, windows, cables) produced in a highly automated winding process, allowing for easy assembly on board. Instead of using low-density foam, BaltiCo uses the composites with truss structure to strengthen the hull and deck structures which help reduce the material consumption. The modular panel can be used in several ways. Either used for a lightweight component on the ship such as replacement of internal wall or superstructure steel, or completely used as the main material for the complete ship.

For the demonstrator, BaltiCo had developed the modular panel into a lightweight catamaran with electrical propulsion, powered by solar energy and produce zero emission. The catamaran consists of 4 main modules (2 hulls and 2 decks) with the length of 10m and light weight of 1.2 tons.

Figure 2 BaltiCo's demonstrator design

With the existing solar panel area of 35 m² the ship can achieve a continuously speed about 12 km/h/ 6.5 kts. The Top speed is 11.5 kts. The manufacturing of the prototype is currently on the process and scheduled to be beginning of 2020.

The catamaran will be built using a filament rod placement process which brings advantages such as weight saving,

modularity, automated manufacturing, and many others. The process starts by producing the GFRP panels using Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). After that, the panels are cut, and construct become a frame. From there, a cross section is built from several frames. In this stage, the filament rod placement machine is ready to transform the cross-section into a carbon truss structure. The filament winding process starts by preparing the carbon filament yarn in the creel and mixing the resin. During the process, the resin is flowing to the resin bath where the carbon filament will be continuously impregnated. During the process, the cross-section staying in the table while the robot head is moving. Unless there is a rotation movement, there is no need to lift the module and fit it into the machine's headstock and tailstock support. Currently, BaltiCo can create hull module truss structure within about 8 hours, and 4 hours for the deck module. The last stage of the process is to cover the truss structure with GFRP single skin using a manual hand lay-up process.

Figure 3 Left: Hull cross sections mounted for filament rod placement process. Right: decks section during manufacturing

In order to choose the best insulation which will be suitable for the modular panel, the demo case screening tests have been planned to be done by RISE. Besides that, to fulfil other properties such as fire, sound, and vibration. BaltiCo created the samples; the related test results were not available at the editorial deadline of the paper at hand.

2.2. Propeller blades made by additive manufacturing

Naval Group (NG) from France is leading this demonstrator. The objective is to develop a representative blade propeller demonstrator using Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) to be a credible alternative to the conventional production processes (metal casting) and to authorize future improvements of propellers performance levels. NG is using the case of the propeller in KRISO Container Ship (KCS), which the scientific community widely uses as a reference case.

Figure 4 Views of the final blade (cavity in red)

A design study had been performed by SIREHNA to optimize the outer blade design and internal structure of the hollow blade. The analysis includes the finite element analysis and computation on the cavitation in the blade. From the study, the hollow blade has a significantly higher outer volume than the reference blade (+62.9%) but a cavity has been arranged in this large volume. The hollow propeller provides significant improvement of the hydrodynamic and transverse performances: on the one hand the cavitation is significantly reduced compared to the reference propeller, thanks to a large increase of the blade thickness, and on the other hand, the weight is reduced by roughly 23% in air and 36% in water.

Through wire deposition (MIG-MAG electric arc wire melting process), NG and Ecole Centrale de Nantes (ECN) are producing test parts from linear deposits to representative test parts of a hollow propeller blade preform geometrical singularities and test block for mechanical characterization test. The production of the representative part has been done, showing good reliability of MIG-MAG electric arc welding process duplex stainless steel, Figure 5, Figure 6. From the experiment, a manufacturing strategy has been determined and a first third scale demonstrator has been built using ECN robot cell and produced in 3 successive stages of a different angle.

Figure 5 (a) Representative singularities of a hollow blade; (b) cavity opening; (c) cavity closure; (d) trailing edge; (e) leading edge; (f) monobead edge

Figure 6 propeller blade demonstrator

2.3. Custom made hull for offshore vessel

This work is led by Damen Schelde Naval Shipbuilding (DSNS) from The Netherlands. The objectives are to scale up the composite technology and capability to design, produce and market complete composite vessels up to 85 m

length that comply with SOLAS and class regulations. Besides designing and approving composite structures complying with class rules, challenges in scaling up the composites technology include pioneering the capability to infuse thick laminates up to 10 meters in height that represent full ship hull structures.

Figure 7 Left: A full-scale hull section for a large offshore vessel; Right: demonstrator highlighted; 6 m high, 5 m width, 2 m long

Unique in this demonstrator project is that the whole cycle from product design, novel resin development, alternative fibre architectures, novel joining solutions, scaling up infusion technology, validation of large composite structures, and its risk based design are being developed and tested, all under the auspices of classification society Bureau Veritas. For product design, Damen Shipyards (DSGo) prepared the baseline design comparing traditional steel scantlings, sandwich panels, and monolithic structures. The structural analysis report contains the analysis approach and results of the hull structure. An analytical approach, as well as finite element analysis (FEM) approach, was performed and documented.

Figure 8 Product design by DSGo, left analytically and right validation by FEA

The process engineering is being performed by the production partners InfraCore Company (ICC) and Aviation Enterprises (AEL) as they are incorporating their composites experience into the design. AEL is preparing the design for production of thick monolithic laminates up to 240 mm in the bottom with smooth transitions towards sandwich side shell structures.

ICC will utilize its unique oblique layers structures for decks representative for helicopter deck, tween deck and tank top. ICC is also responsible for the design and production of the bulkheads, as well as the connection and assembly strategy of all structural elements. Here AEL's scaling up of the more traditional sandwich layouts will be compared with ICC oblique layers structures in terms of ease for production, robustness and cost. As such, also ICC is targeting to infuse a section, representative for the bulkhead, vertically, in order to demonstrate that the key challenge of a 6 meter high infusion, can be performed by its oblique layered technology as well. Also robustness will be demonstrated as impact representative for actual helicopter emergency loading will be demonstrated on the oblique layers helicopter deck as well as on the sandwich side shell. Finally, the hydrocarbon fire resulting from a helicopter crash will also be tested on the impacted ICC helicopter deck.

The novel resin has been developed by EVONIK in various iterations in close collaboration with the production partners focusing on the best balance between flow characteristics at different infusion temperatures and mechanical properties such as toughness. The strategy for the vertical infusion has been developed by both production partners AEL as well as ICC. Extensive trials have been performed from small scale up to full 6-meter-

high for which specific tooling has been developed. Currently, the steel mold for vertical infusion of the steel outer shell has been produced by DSNS, and is made available to AEL for trials and eventual production of the hull section. ICC has managed to infuse its panel vertically up to the targeted 6 meters in height. This panel represents the hull shell laminates, but now with ICC's oblique layers fiber architectures.

Figure 9 Left: laminate layup on steel hull tool at AEL, with insert picture of 240 mm monolithic laminate in hull bottom. Mid and right: Successful 6 meter vertical infusion by Infracore infused with Evonik's novel toughened resin Albidur® VE3940

ICC has developed novel joining solutions enabling an efficient assembly of large composites decks and bulkheads into the global hull assembly relying on adhesively bonded joints as well as shape locked fixations and overlaminates where required by classification. These joints will be tested in full scale cruciform tests and in the large scale box.

Figure 10 Left: Tween deck to hull joint, Right: top deck to hull joint development by Infracore

TNO will perform full scale tests for validation of design, quality management and structural performance. BV, as a Classification Society, offers consultancy and advice, resulting in a smart track to approval guideline. The testing in accordance with approval process starts from the raw materials homologation, material coupons tests, specimen testing (joint testing), and large-scale testing. A representative box will be built, having the same scantlings and full scale joints as the actual ship. This box is subjected to a bending load, resulting in the stress in the panels being the same as in the actual vessel, and will demonstrate the ability to successfully model large composite structures. The full-scale demonstrator section will be subjected to impact tests, representing helicopter crash and impacts with floating objects.

The process definition for approval has been developed in close cooperation with RISE, NMTF and BV. BV has defined a first draft of the approval process to be considered within RAMSSES, and the Damen demo will serve a reference case for the smart track to approval (STA) process which will be described in the next chapter.

Concerning fire safety, a HazId (Hazard Identification) has been performed with RISE and BV to address all fire risks, including the helicopter deck in composite materials. Fire performance criteria have been defined as well and will be tested and validated at RISE facilities.

Figure 11 (a) Large scale box (8m x 2m x 2m) validating and testing design to loads representative to global bending forces representative for the actual vessel; (b) test setup developed by TNO including two cylinders of 1000 tons each; (c) FEA validation of shear stress of the box (deflected)

3. Measures for more agility regarding material innovation in the maritime industry

A set of measures to improve the material innovation capability in shipbuilding was suggested in the latest report of the ISSC Specialist Committee *Materials and Fabrication Technology* (Josefsson et al). RAMSSES is following several strategic activities which are in line with these measures. The most prominent ones – the creation of a materials innovation platform and elaboration of a smart track to approval – are discussed below.

3.1. Materials innovation platform

Validated information and knowledge from outside the RAMSSES community, lessons learnt from the RAMSSES demonstrator cases which is relevant to a wider community as well as test results from the project and from previous projects will be stored in the RAMSSES central knowledge repository. This knowledge is both accessible by all project partners and partly – respecting Intellectual Property Rights protection of project results – to an external community. The knowledge repository will become the kernel of a maritime material innovation platform which is currently being set up. Further to the already ongoing process of collecting reports and data about advanced materials and their use in maritime application, the innovation platform can be used to collect and discuss ideas for further research and to enhance collaboration. After the end of RAMSSES, the maritime innovation platform will be taken over by the coordinator of the renowned European network for lightweight applications at sea, E-LASS (www.e-lass.eu), thus giving added value to the organization and turning it into an even more sustainable network.

3.2. The smart track to approval

There is limited field history of FRP composite structures in commercial application on SOLAS ships. Approval of the materials from a mechanical perspective requires a thorough testing procedure, and from a fire safety perspective it is not possible to refer to the prescriptive regulations in SOLAS since the material is combustible. It is instead necessary to approve the fire safety design and arrangements as based on a risk assessment which demonstrates that equivalent fire safety is achieved. These procedures need to be done case by case and are often time-consuming and costly. Therefore, the RAMSSES project is developing and testing a new approach referred to as a ‘smart track to approval’ (STA). It provides recommendations for a more standardized approval procedure for alternative design, regarding both mechanical and fire safety. It will work for different extents of structures and will include examples of promising solutions, to make the design and approval of new material structure solutions less costly, less time consuming, more efficient, more harmonized and quality assured. The STA principle is based on the experience gained during RAMSSES and from previous research and commercial projects. It is also based on sharing knowledge with other industrial sectors, e.g. aeronautics, railway and automotive, and on the creation of a database with standardized performance of FRP composite materials and pre-approved solutions. The objective is not to compromise safety but to have a smarter approach than today to reach at least the same safety level.

The STA is composed of two layers: one led by approving authorities and one led by the shipyards, engineering or design offices. The STA will be the first step to prepare an *Approval In Principle* (AIP), leading to the certification or the classification of a vessel or a part of the vessel. The STA is developed in the RAMSSES project to propose an alternative to the prescriptive rules concerning for innovative materials in the shipbuilding industry, see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** The ambition is that the FTA will mainly be used for the approval of alternative design solutions in accordance with the circular MSC.1/Circ.1455 or MSC/Circ.1002.

Figure 12 Smart Track to Approval, process overview

From the results of demonstrator case risk analyses, the STA will propose standard risk scenarios, standard tests, standard solutions and a database to lookup for reusable data. The quantitative analyses are currently carried out on a case-by-case basis. The aim is to develop standard risk scenarios covering a range of similar applications. These can be referred to in the future without the need to carry out extensive quantitative analyses or tests. During the next phase of RAMSSES project, this STA approach will be applied to the demonstrator case developed by the shipyard Damen to demonstrate its feasibility and efficiency.

The STA concept was presented on E-LASS seminars several times, receiving valuable and positive feedback. Meanwhile, RAMSSES initiated a collaboration with the ongoing European project FIBRESHIP which is pursuing similar objectives. The two projects agreed to combine their proposals for developing the approval processes for innovative materials and to present them at the IMO’s session SDC7 (February 03, 2020).

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